

IMPROVING COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE SKILLS THROUGH ROLE PLAYING ACTIVITY

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to the importance of role playing in teaching the English language to upper intermediate level learners. The most important issues needed for the organization of role play activities are looked through. The article also describes the author's comments based on the method of observation and experience in teaching. Recommendations for the targeted organization of role-playing games are given.

Keywords: role play, learning environment, drama activity, collaborative learning, interaction.

Introduction. English as a foreign language is tutored at high seminaries, sodalities, universities etc. Like any other subjects, English can be tutored by a constructive or the communicative approach. Throughout the completion of the composition lots of accoutrements, literature and other coffers were revised by us. By probing we aimed to know whether the scores of speaking tutored by using role play better or not by com- par in the scholars' scores ahead and after being tutored by using role play fashion, to develop learners' speaking chops through communicative language conditioning and games.

Research Methodology. We selected modern approaches and methods (through activities and games) of teaching English to students. It is used comparative method in this article.

Statement of the problem. Role play is one of the most topical subjects in ultramodern styles of tutoring English. At present utmost of the trained preceptors of our country are tutoring English using different conditioning and games in their classes. So, we wanted to know the learners' and preceptors' perception of using these styles and approaches, how they apply communicative speaking conditioning and games, rather than Traditional Approach. To compensate for the limitations of the traditional language tutoring styles, new ways of tutoring have been introduced in EFL and ESP settings to ameliorate learners' capacities to use English in real life situational surrounds.

Using Conditioning lawyers tutoring practices that develop communicative capability in authentic surrounds. still, the propositions and practices of CLT have faced colorful challenges in EFL surrounds. therefore, this study explores the effectiveness and significance of conditioning and games in tutoring English to scholars, with the recommendation that their views be considered in opinions regarding the integration of CLT into our Education system. This means that success of learning a foreign language depends on how well learners have developed their communicative capabilities and how important they're suitable to apply this knowledge of language in real life situations.

To make teaching more intriguing and meaningful English preceptors use different types of tutoring styles and approaches. In Uzbekistan, the main focus of communicative language teaching (within conditioning and games) system is to help the learners' scholars' pupils to learn a language so that they can use it to communicate meaningfully in any real-life situation. The styles assume that the learners will be suitable to communicate socially on an everyday

base or expert English language speakers on finance and business sphere. The communicative approach makes preceptors and scholars consider language in terms of the communicative functions. The important advantage revealed by us is the study of language through kinds, which concentrate on different types of role-playing conditioning and games, from which both preceptors and language learners can profit.

New teaching approaches through conditioning offer new literacy strategies adding diversity and inflexibility to being styles and forms of classroom practice. Each approach can be successfully espoused in the English language classroom either in combination with others or independently. The learners' requirements are determined by learners' cerebral characteristics as well as other factors impacting the literacy teaching process and it should be decisive in an approach selection. Looking through the new handbooks for learners we can notice that they're written on the base of new teaching styles especially their authors pay further attention to harkening appreciation, and speaking for developing pronunciation, speech and understanding at the same time of speaking through conditioning and games.

First of all, the composition reveals that enforcing role-play conditioning develops scholars' speaking chops rather than the other conditioning. This type of interactive exertion is more charming to the learners because they find it funny to play someone additional part. The maturity of the scholars conceded that their speaking and communication chops are developed and come more as a result of nonstop use of the part play conditioning in language literacy. What's intriguing, the learners told to the schoolteacher that when they used English during an ordinary assignment, some of them felt stressed and bullied.

The schoolteacher also observed that when conducting the exploration assignments nearly all of the scholars were really involved in the exercises. Probing this content, we organized a check with the class before starting the exploration about role play conditioning. During the assignment of trial, the scholars tried their stylish to get into the places and use only English (although there were always some scholars who despite being told three times not to use the mama lingo they would continue doing so). likewise, some scholars claimed that they had overcome their fear of speaking because they had relatively important time devoted only to speaking in the target language. likewise, the learners also liked the fact that they could move in the classroom when, for illustration, visiting trip agencies.

Also, working in dyads and groups was appealing to the scholars, because they could overcome their fear of speaking in front of people with whom they didn't have a close relationship. Altogether, role-play seems to be an effective speaking exercise and the preceptors shouldn't forget to apply such an exercise from time to time. What the scholars told the schoolteacher after finishing the last trial assignment was that such a type of task had numerous benefits but having such an exercise during each week might be a little boring and predictable for the scholars. In addition, drama as another type of communicative language exertion could always be extended and used as a starting-point for other conditioning. The theme can act as an encouragement for discussion or written work going far beyond the acting out of scenes. Dramatic conditioning can therefore be integrated into a course, which in turn could lead to them being exploited in terms of the language syllabus, for illustration the literacy of vocabulary, indeed of structures. As matters stand now, drama and dramatic conditioning tend not to live as a special area within the syllabus separate from all other language conditioning, but they frequently lap with them. Maybe one of the topmost

advantages to be gained from the use of drama is that the language learners come more confident in their use of English by passing the language in operation.

The pupil-centeredness essential in all dramatic conditioning also improves scholars' maturity and provocation, and the physical involvement contained in drama along with the conception of learning language through action is an effective variation on the system of Total Physical Response and other holistic approaches to language tutoring, where the learner rather than the language or indeed the schoolteacher is at the center of the literacy process. Drama in the English language classroom is eventually necessary because it gives learners the chance to use their own personalities. It draws upon scholars' natural capacities to imitate and express themselves, and if well-handled should arouse interest and imagination.

Results. Having had 20 times of work experience as a school teacher of English it can be told without any vacillation that part playing and drama conditioning are the veritably chance for scholars to ameliorate their communicative language chops. First when we began tutoring at the university my scholars were asked to use these conditioning in the form of acting out discourses. Those times maturity of scholars was shy, some of them were embarrassed, some of them were hysterical of making pronunciation miscalculations. But anyway, practice makes perfect, the final result wasn't only conspicuous, but it was brilliant. From time to time they began to understand and appreciate its significance and preferred to acting out similar kind of conditioning as much as possible. Occasionally motifs for their exchanges were given to them by the schoolteacher, occasionally it was over to them to choose an applicable content for the assignment to communicate with each other. After some months they got used to doing part play conditioning and set up out them veritably useful way of perfecting their speaking chops. Through these interactive conditioning one can ameliorate not only his/her speaking chops, but also one can ameliorate their pronunciation, vocabulary and alphabet chops.

Discussion. The most intriguing and pleasurable thing which attracts us further and further is that the exertion seems more intriguing by wearing their part costumes and make-up and make the literacy process as fun for them.

It was always conspicuous that this helps scholars feel freely and helps them to ameliorate their critical thinking capacities. Because when they act out part play conditioning wearing their part costumes it's conspicuous that they bear themselves like real characters of their places and enjoy doing this. occasionally they wear the croakers', preceptors', culinarians', shop sidekicks' or the trip agent's livery. occasionally they try to act out the places of some film star' or vocalizers' places. Surely, in order to act out their places, they've to learn the new vocabulary nearly connected with those professions. They try to do their bests to act out their places more and more every time.

Conclusion. Eventually, we can say that part-playing exertion is a important and effective tutoring system for learners and can be acclimated to deliver any literacy objects from simple to complex generalities. In addition to this we can say that, this learning terrain supports pedagogical and practical knowledge. likewise, it facilitates to internalize tutoring practice. The success lies in the construction and delivery with careful facilitation. It's a great system for preceptors and coaches as it is an amusing exertion which makes every pupil be involved in the process.

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